

The Quantum Primordial Black Holes and Relic Gravitational Waves

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(Received 2 September, 2025)

This paper based on the previously obtained results begins a study into the problem how parameters of the Relic Gravitational Waves (**RGW**) are shifted due to quantum-gravitational corrections to primordial black holes in the early Universe. Explicit formulae have been derived for the corresponding shifts of the wave equation, adiabatic vacuum approximation boundaries, the energy of each created **RGW**, power spectra of all cosmological expansion stages. It is shown that some of the parameters acquire higher values, specifically the adiabatic bound for the frequencies and the energy of each created **RGW**. Other parameters retain their values but their domains of definition are shifted, for example, the present power spectrum of **RGWs**. In the concluding part, the problems for further relevant studies are formulated.

PACS numbers: 11.10.-z, 11.15.Ha, 12.38.Bx

Keywords: quantum primordial black holes, inflationary cosmology, quantum-gravitational corrections, relic gravitational waves

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17949234>

1. Introduction

In the last twenty years numerous works devoted to a primordial black holes mechanisms of their formation and effects. It is worth noting both interesting reviews on this topic [1] and important results concerning specific problems [2]-[4]. These articles and other works in the field of primordial black holes motivated the present research. The primordial black holes (**pbhs**) [5]-[7] in the Early Universe are due to gravitational collapse of the high-density matter [8]. In [9]-[11] a sufficiently accurate estimate of the mass **pbhs** $M(t)$ formed during the period of time t since the Big Bang has been obtained. And for small times close to the Planckian time $t = t_p \approx 10^{-43}$ s, the mass of **pbhs** is close to the Planck mass $M(t) \approx 10^{-5}g$.

In [12]-[14] author uses for such **pbhs** the name **quantum pbhs** (or **qpbhs**) introduced in [15],[16] and notes that quantum-gravitational effects for these objects could be significant. Of particular interest are **pbhs** arising in the

preinflationary epoch. In [17] a semiclassical approximation was used to study the problem of scalar perturbations due to such **pbhs**. But, considering that all the processes in this case proceed at very high energies E close to the Planckian $E \simeq E_p$, the inclusion of quantum-gravity corrections **qgcs** for these black holes in this pattern is necessary if quantum gravity exists [18]. Despite the fact that presently there is no self-consistent theory of quantum gravity, a consensus is reached on correctness of some approaches to the theory, specifically, replacement of the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle (**HUP**) by the Generalized Uncertainty Principle (**GUP**) on going to high (Planck) energies, used in this paper.

As demonstrated in [12]-[14], the quantum-gravitational corrections for **qpbhs** in the pre-inflation era may lead to shifts of the inflation parameters and of the corresponding cosmological perturbations, to the non-gaussianity enhancement of these perturbations, etc. In this paper the author applies the methods developed in [12]-[14] to the physics of the Relic

Gravitational Waves (**RGW**). In particular, within the suggested pattern, the author presents explicit formulae for the corresponding shifts of the wave equation, adiabatic vacuum approximation boundaries, energy of each created **RGW**, power spectra of all cosmological expansion stages. In conclusion the problems for further studies are formulated.

In what follows the normalization $c = \hbar = 1$ is used, for which we have $G = l_p^2$.

2. Necessary Preliminary Information in Brief

In [12] and [13] the primordial black holes **pbhs**, having small radii in the pre-inflation era, have been studied with the Schwarzschild-de Sitter (SdS) metric [17] in de Sitter space. The metric in the explicit form is as follows:

$$ds^2 = -f(\tilde{r})dt^2 + \frac{d\tilde{r}^2}{f(\tilde{r})} + \tilde{r}^2 d\Omega^2 \quad (1)$$

where $f(\tilde{r}) = 1 - 2GM/\tilde{r} - \Lambda\tilde{r}^2/3 = 1 - 2GM/\tilde{r} - \tilde{r}^2/L^2$, $L = \sqrt{3/\Lambda} = H_0^{-1}$, M - black hole mass, Λ - cosmological constant, and $L = H_0^{-1}$ is the Hubble radius.

As demonstrated in [13], because of smallness of the **pbhs** under study, for them the formulae for black holes with the Schwarzschild metric are valid with a high accuracy [20],[19]

$$ds^2 = -\left(1 - \frac{2MG}{r}\right) dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{2MG}{r}\right)^{-1} dr^2 - r^2 d\Omega^2. \quad (2)$$

Specifically, the formula for the radius r_M of a black hole with the mass M :

$$r_M = 2GM. \quad (3)$$

Assuming that the dimensions of the above-mentioned **pbhs** with the (SdS) metric are within the domain close to the Planck, i.e. $r_H \propto l_p$, it is inferred that their quantum-gravitational corrections (**qgcs**) may be significant. Because of this, such **pbhs** in [13] are called the *quantum pbhs* or **qpbhs**. To calculate **qgcs** for **qpbhs** in [13] the Generalized Uncertainty Principle (**GUP**) has been used in the form [21]

$$[X, P] = i\hbar \exp\left(\frac{\alpha^2 l_p^2 P^2}{\hbar^2}\right),$$

$$(\delta X)(\delta P) \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} \left\langle \exp\left(\frac{\alpha^2 l_p^2 P^2}{\hbar^2}\right) \right\rangle. \quad (4)$$

As a result, there is a possibility for the existence of a Planck Schwarzschild black hole, and accordingly of a Schwarzschild sphere (further referred to as "minimal"), with the minimal mass M_0 and the minimal radius r_{min} (formula (20) in [21]) that is a theoretical minimal length $r_{min} \doteq r_0$:

$$r_0 = l_{min} = (\delta X)_0 = \sqrt{\frac{e}{2}} \alpha l_p, \quad M_0 = \frac{\alpha \sqrt{e}}{2\sqrt{2}} m_p, \quad (5)$$

where in (4),(5) α - model-dependent parameters on the order of 1, e - base of natural logarithms, and $r_0 \propto l_p$, $M_0 \propto m_p$.

With the use of the normalization $G = l_p^2$ adopted in [21], temperature of a Schwarzschild black hole having the mass M (the radius R) [19] in a semi-classical approximation takes the form

$$T_H = \frac{1}{8\pi GM}. \quad (6)$$

Within the scope of GUP (4), the temperature T_H with regard to (**qgc**) is of the form ((23) and (25) in [21])

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{H,q} &= \frac{1}{8\pi MG} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right) = \frac{1}{8\pi MG} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^2\right)\right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{8\pi MG} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2e}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^2 + \frac{5}{8e^2}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^4 + \frac{49}{48e^3}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^6 + \dots\right), \tag{7}
 \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{H,q} &= \frac{1}{8\pi M_q G}, M_q = M \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right); \\
 r_{M_q} &= 2M_q G = r_M \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right) = r_M \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^2\right)\right), \tag{8}
 \end{aligned}$$

where M_q and r_{M_q} are respectively the initial black-hole mass and event horizon radius considering **qgcs** caused by GUP (4). Here $W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)$ – value at the corresponding point of the Lambert W-function $W(u)$ satisfying the equation (formulae (1.5) in [22] and (9) in [21])

$$W(u) e^{W(u)} = u. \tag{9}$$

$W(u)$ is the multifunction for complex variable $u = x + yi$. However, for real $u = x, -1/e \leq u < 0, W(u)$ is the single-valued continuous function having two branches denoted by $W_0(u)$ and $W_{-1}(u)$, and for real $u = x, u \geq 0$ there is only one branch $W_0(u)$ [22].

Obviously, the quantum-gravitational correction (**qgc**) (7) presents a *deformation* (or more exactly, the *quantum deformation* of a classical black-holes theory from the viewpoint of the paper [23] with the deformation parameter M_0^2/M^2):

$$\frac{M_0^2}{M^2} = \frac{r_0^2}{r_M^2} = \frac{l_{min}^2}{r_M^2}, \tag{10}$$

where $r_0 = l_{min}$ is the horizon radius of minimal **pbh** from formula (5).

It should be noted that this deformation parameter

$$l_{min}^2/r_M^2 \doteq \alpha_{r_M} \tag{11}$$

has been introduced by the author in his earlier works [24]–[29], where he studied deformation of quantum mechanics at Planck scales in terms of the deformed quantum mechanical density matrix.

As seen, $W(0) = 0$ is an obvious solution for the equation (9). For black hole with great mass $M \gg m_p$ we have

$$\exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^2\right)\right) \approx 1. \tag{12}$$

and therefore for such black holes necessitates no consideration of **qgcs**. But in the case of small black holes we have

$$\exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^2\right)\right) > 1. \tag{13}$$

It should be noted that, with the expansion $\exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^2\right)\right)$ in terms of the small parameter $\alpha_{r_M} = (r_0/r_M)^2$, in formula (7) one can easily obtain the small-parameter expansion of the inverse number $\exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^2\right)\right)$, and also of all the

integer powers for this exponent, specifically for its square $\exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^2\right)\right)$.

In [17] for inflationary scenario the metric (1) is conveniently described in terms of the conformal time η :

$$ds^2 = a^2(\eta) \left\{ -d\eta^2 + \left(1 + \frac{\mu^3 \eta^3}{r^3}\right)^{4/3} \left[\left(\frac{1 - \mu^3 \eta^3 / r^3}{1 + \mu^3 \eta^3 / r^3}\right)^2 dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2 \right] \right\}, \tag{14}$$

where $\mu = (GMH_0/2)^{1/3}$, H_0 is the de Sitter-Hubble parameter and scale factor, a is the conformal time function η :

$$a(\eta) = -1/(H_0\eta), \eta < 0, \tag{15}$$

where r satisfies the condition $r_0 < r < \infty$ and a value of $r_0 = -\mu\eta$ in the reference frame of (14) conforms to singularity of the back hole.

In virtue (3), μ may be given as

$$\mu = (r_M H_0 / 4)^{1/3}, \tag{16}$$

where r_M is the radius of a black hole with the SdS Schwarzschild-de Sitter metric (1).

Then for $\mu = const$ from [17] in [13] we consider three patterns: steady-state (when for a **qpbh** there are no accretion processes and no emission), for the same **qpbh** the two other patterns are associated with the processes of

absorption or emission, respectively.

These three patterns involve the equation

$$\mu = const = (r_M H_0 / 4)^{1/3} = (r_{M_q} H_{0,q} / 4)^{1/3}, \tag{17}$$

where $r_{M_q} = R_q$ from the general formula (8), and in the general case $r_{M_q}, H_{0,q}$ are values of r_M, H_0 , respectively, with due regard for the above **qgcs** (formulae (7),(8)).

Based on the last formula (17) and formulae (7),(11),(8), it directly follows that

$$\begin{aligned} H_{0,q} &= H_0 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right) = \\ &= H_0 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right). \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Then **qgc** for the scale factor $a(\eta)$ (15)

$$\begin{aligned} a(\eta) &\rightarrow a(\eta)_q \doteq -1/(H_{0,q}\eta) = -1/(H_0 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right)\eta) = \\ &= -1/(H_0 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right)\eta) = a(\eta) \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right), \eta < 0, \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

and for the Hubble parameter in general case

$$H(\eta) \doteq H$$

$$H = a'(\eta)/a^2(\eta) \mapsto H_q(\eta) = a'(\eta)_q/a^2(\eta)_q. \tag{20}$$

As directly follows from the last formula, in this pattern H_0 and H are identically transformed, i.e. we have

$$H \mapsto H_q = H \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2} W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \alpha_{r_M} \right) \right). \quad (21)$$

Definition 2.1

Let us call the above-defined deformation M_q -**deformation** the *quantum deformation* (formulae (10),(11)) due to **qgcs** for the Schwarzschild **qpbh** of the mass M , calling the associated "shifts" of various quantities (for example, formulae (18)–(21),... $-M_q$ -**shifts**).

3. Some General Commentaries on Quantum Primordial Black Holes and RGW

One can specify three different scenarios for generation of the relic gravitational waves (**RGWs**) within the pattern when **pbhs** exist in the early Universe.

3.A As the inflation theory leads to the generation of **RGWs** (tensor perturbations) and the calculations in [12],[13] demonstrate that **qpbhs** formed in the pre-inflation era shift the inflation parameters (M_q -**shifts**), such **qpbhs** cause the corresponding shifts of the parameters of **RGW**. This paper is devoted precisely to the case.

3.B **RGWs** generated by light **pbhs**. The process was first studied in [30].

3.C The well-known generation mechanism of gravitational waves from merging of black holes is also valid for **pbhs** (see [31]).

3.1. M_q -deformation of the Wave Equation and the Adiabatic Vacuum Approximation

The results obtained in [12],[13] and briefly considered in the previous section may

be applied to studies of **RGWs** in the early Universe. This is important because modern gravitational-wave cosmology becomes an increasingly precise science. This necessitates taking into consideration the contributions made by quantum **pbhs**.

In what follows the author uses the symbols and results from [32]–[35]. To derive the gravitational-wave solutions, it is convenient to represent the metric in the following form:

$$\bar{g}_{ij} = g_{ij} + h_{ij}(x_i) \quad (i, j = 0, 1, 2, 3),$$

$$|h_{ij}| \ll |g_{ij}| \quad (22)$$

and

$$h_{00} = h_{0\alpha} = 0 \quad (\alpha = 1, 2, 3).. \quad (23)$$

With the additional (gauge) conditions set by the equation (23), the following conditions are imposed:

$$h^{ij}{}_{;j} = 0, . \quad (24)$$

Here the semi-colon denotes a covariant derivative with respect to the background metric (25):

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + a(t)^2 [dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2]$$

$$= a(\eta)^2 [-d\eta^2 + dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2]. \quad (25)$$

Then we operate with the conformal coordinates and the conformal time η .

Next, similar to [32],[33], we introduce the ansatz

$$h_\alpha{}^\beta(t, \mathbf{x}) = h(t) G_\alpha{}^\beta(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{x}), \quad (26)$$

where $G_\alpha{}^\beta$ is a combination of plane-waves solutions $exp(\pm ikx)$, involving the two polarizations of the wave mentioned above, and fulfill the following:

$$G_{\alpha;\gamma}{}^{\beta;\gamma} = -k^2 G_\alpha{}^\beta, \quad G_{\alpha;\beta}{}^\alpha = G_\alpha{}^\alpha = 0, . \quad (27)$$

Arriving, like in the general case, to the evolution equation for the temporal part of the wave in terms of the conformal time

$$h''(k, \eta) + 2\frac{a'}{a}h'(k, \eta) + k^2h(k, \eta) = 0. \quad (28)$$

This equation, with the use of the ansatz $h(k, \eta) = \mu(k, \eta)/a(\eta)$, leads to the Lifshitz equation

$$\mu''(k, \eta) + \left(k^2 - \frac{a''(\eta)}{a(\eta)} \right) \mu(k, \eta) = 0. \quad (29)$$

Here $k = |\mathbf{k}|$ is the wave-number relating the wave length and frequency $k = 2\pi a/\lambda = a\omega$.

For the pattern under study, according to (18)-(21), in the above formulae there are substitutions:

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &\rightarrow ds_q^2, k \rightarrow k_q = |\mathbf{k}_q| = a_q\omega; h(k, \eta) \rightarrow h(k_q, \eta) \doteq h(k, \eta)_q = \mu(k, \eta)_q/a(\eta)_q; \\ \mu(k, \eta) &\rightarrow \mu(k, \eta)_q \doteq \mu(k_q, \eta). \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Then for the general wave solutions the results from [35],[32],[33] are valid with shifts of the principal parameters due to M_q -**deformation**. Specifically, since (29) describes an oscillator with varying frequency and the condition $k_q^2 \gg \frac{a_q''}{a_q} = \frac{a''}{a}$ is valid, the solutions for M_q -**deformed** equation (29) are obtained similar to [35]:

$$\mu(k_q, \eta)'' + \left(k_q^2 - \frac{a''(\eta)_q}{a(\eta)_q} \right) \mu(k_q, \eta) = 0. \quad (31)$$

As $\mu(k_q, \eta) = e^{\pm ik_q\eta}$, i.e. high-frequency waves have the adiabatically changing M_q -**deformed** amplitude $h_q = a_q^{-1} \sin(k_q\eta + \phi)$, wave amplitudes in the expanding Universe decrease adiabatically according to $a_q^{-1} = a^{-1} \exp(-\frac{1}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}))$. The change is more abrupt than in the initial (non M_q -**deformed**) case because $\exp(-\frac{1}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M})) > 1$. For the initial solutions $h(k, \eta)_q = \mu(k, \eta)_q/a(\eta)_q$ from (30), the wave amplitudes decrease as $a_q^{-2} = a^{-2} \exp(-W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}))$, i.e. the decrease is more and more enhanced.

For $k_q^2 \ll \frac{a_q''}{a_q} = \frac{a''}{a}$, the general solution of the deformed-variant equation (29) is a linear

combination of the two solutions

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{1,q} &= a(\eta)_q = \mu_1 \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right), \\ \mu_{2,q} &= a(\eta)_q \int d\eta a(\eta)_q^{-2} \\ &= \mu_2 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right). \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

It is shown in [35] that in the expanding Universe, similar to the canonical case, $\mu_{1,q}$ grows faster than $\mu_{2,q}$. But in the case under study the growth is damped by the factors $\exp(\frac{1}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}))$ and $\exp(-\frac{1}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}))$, this damping being the lower the higher the radius of the initial **qpbh**. Nevertheless, in the course of time $\mu_{1,q}$ is domineering and, considering the formulae in (30), the amplitude $h(k, \eta)_q$ remains constant so long as $k_q^2 \ll \frac{a_q''}{a_q} = \frac{a''}{a}$.

Note that, due to the formulae in (18)-(21) and (30), we have $k_q^2 < k^2$ and hence

$$\left(k^2 \ll \frac{a''}{a} \right) \Rightarrow k_q^2 \ll \frac{a_q''}{a_q} = \frac{a''}{a}. \quad (33)$$

In the case when the condition (33) is violated, the condition $k_q^2 < \frac{a_q''}{a_q} = \frac{a''}{a}$ is fulfilled instead, and the behavior of the amplitude $h(k, \eta)_q$ is no longer adiabatic and, similar to the general case, so we observe the phenomenon called the "parametric" amplification of gravitational waves [35].

As $k_q^2 \ll \frac{a_q''}{a_q} (k_q^2 \gg \frac{a_q''}{a_q})$ is considered inside (outside) of the Hubble radius $r_H = 2\pi a H(\eta)$ and as from (18)-(21) it is obvious that $r_H = r_{H_q}$, we have

$$(k < 2\pi a H(\eta)) \Rightarrow k_q < 2\pi a_q H(\eta)_q. \quad (34)$$

But, considering the inequality $k > k_q$, the condition $k_q > 2\pi a_q H(\eta)_q$ is not following from the condition $k > 2\pi a H(\eta)$. Because of this, for the condition outside of the Hubble radius $r_{H_q} = r_H = 2\pi a H(\eta)$ be fulfilled in the case $k_q^2 \gg \frac{a_q''}{a_q} = \frac{a''}{a}$, the initial wave-number k should be higher.

However, as this is taken into consideration, the initial vacuum amplitude of **RGWs** $h \propto A(k) \propto k$ [35] is lowered $h_q \propto A(k_q) \propto k_q < k$.

Further, within the scope of the M_q -**deformation**, the M_q -**shifts** are arising due to the corresponding multiplicative additions in the expression for the known quantities (18)-(21). In all cases the factors involved are the value for $\exp(\frac{1}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}))$ and its (not necessarily integer) positive and negative powers. Considering the substitutions, in particular, a solution for the M_q -**deformed RGWs** equation (28) takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} h_{ij}(\eta, \mathbf{x})_q &= \int \left(A_{(k)} h_{ij}^{(k)}(\mathbf{k}, x)_q + A_{(k)}^\dagger h_{ij}^{(k)*}(\mathbf{k}_q, x)_q \right) d^3 k_q \\ &= \exp\left(\frac{3}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) \int \left(A_{(k_q)} h_{ij}^{(k_q)}(\mathbf{k}_q, x) + A_{(k_q)}^\dagger h_{ij}^{(k_q)*}(\mathbf{k}_q, x) \right) d^3 k. \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

And for $h_{ij}^{(k_q)}(\mathbf{k}_q, x)$ in this case we have

$$h_{ij}^{(k_q)}(\mathbf{k}_q, x) = \frac{\sqrt{8\pi}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} e_{ij}(\mathbf{k}_q) \frac{\mu(k_q, \eta)}{a(\eta)_q} e^{i\mathbf{k}_q \cdot \mathbf{x}}, \quad (36)$$

where $e_{ij}(\mathbf{k}_q)$, as in [32], contains both polarizations of the wave, and the functions

$\mu(k_q, \eta)$ are solutions of the equation (31). Note that the orthogonality conditions (formulae (2.28),(2.29) in [33]) for $h_{ij}^{(k_q)}(\mathbf{k}_q, x)$ and $\mu(k_q, \eta)$ remain valid and we have that

$$-i \int \left(h_{ij}^{(k_q)}(\mathbf{k}_q, x) h_{ij}^{(k'_q)*'}(\mathbf{k}'_q, x) - h_{ij}^{(k'_q)'}(\mathbf{k}'_q, x) h_{ij}^{(k_q)*}(\mathbf{k}_q, x) \right) d^{n-1} x = \delta(\mathbf{k}_q - \mathbf{k}'_q) \quad (37)$$

with

$$\mu_{(k_q)} \mu_{(k_q)}^{*'} - \mu_{(k_q)}^* \mu_{(k_q)'} = i. \quad (38)$$

Further calculations are associated with the initial results from [32],[33]. Similar to the general case, (taking no account of M_q -**shifts**) for the state equation of a perfect fluid in the spatially

flat FRW Universe we use the notation

$$p = (\gamma - 1)\rho, \quad (39)$$

where γ is a constant.

Then the corresponding M_q -deformed Einstein equation is of the form

$$\left(\frac{a'_q}{a_q^2}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi}{3}\rho, \quad \rho' + 3\frac{a'_q}{a_q}(\rho + p) = 0. \quad (40)$$

It is obvious that the second of the M_q -deformed Einstein equations is equivalent to the nondeformed case as $a'_q/a_q = a'/a$.

It should be noted that, with respect to the canonical case, the first of the above Einstein equations is changed due to the factor $\exp(-W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}))$ in its left side. As shown in [13], multiplying the right side of this equation by the inverse quantity $\exp(W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}))$, then redefining ρ and p , we can obtain an equivalent equation.

In this way (40) is rewritten in the equivalent form [13] as

$$\left(\frac{a'}{a^2}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi}{3}\rho_q; \rho_q \doteq \rho \exp\left(W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right); \quad \rho'_q + 3\frac{a'}{a}(\rho_q + p_q) = 0; p_q \doteq p \exp\left(W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right). \quad (41)$$

It should be noted that, considering M_q -deformation, (39) is retained

$$p_q = (\gamma - 1)\rho_q, \quad (42)$$

Similar to the general form of the solution (40) [33]:

$$a(\eta)_q = a_{i,q} \left(\frac{a_{i,q}H_{i,q}}{l}\right)^l \left(\eta - \eta_i + \frac{l}{a_{i,q}H_{i,q}}\right)^l, \quad (43)$$

where $a_{i,q}$, $H_{i,q}$ are respectively the initial M_q -deformed values of the scale factor and the Hubble function, η_i and the conformal time for $l = 2/(3\gamma - 2)$, as in [32],[33]. However, according to (18)-(21) $a_{i,q}H_{i,q} = a_iH_i$, the expressions in brackets in (43) for the nondeformed and the M_q -deformed cases are coincident and we obtain

$a(\eta)_q = a(\eta) \exp(\frac{1}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}))$ in a complete agreement with (19).

Based on the above-mentioned formulae, it is found that $\eta_{l,q} = \eta - \eta_i + l/(a_{i,q}H_{i,q}) = \eta_l = \eta - \eta_i + l/(a_iH_i)$. Then similarly [33] the M_q -deformed Lifshitz equation (31) reduces to the M_q -deformed Bessel equation

$$\mu''(k_q, \eta) + \left[k_q^2 - \frac{l(l-1)}{(\eta_l)^2}\right] \mu(k_q, \eta) = 0. \quad (44)$$

The solutions can be written in terms of M_q -deformed Hankel functions as

$$\mu_l(\eta)_q = \mu_l(k_q, \eta) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} k_q^{-1/2} x_{l,q}^{1/2} \times \left[D_{1l} H_{l-\frac{1}{2}}^{(1)}(x_{l,q}) + D_{2l} H_{l-\frac{1}{2}}^{(2)}(x_{l,q}) \right], \quad (45)$$

where now $x_{l,q} = k_q \eta_l$, D_{1l} and D_{2l} are integration constants as [33].

Next we assume, like in the general case [32],[33], fulfillment of the condition for the adiabatic vacuum approximation [37], necessitating only that the creation of particles by a slow change in the initial state is minimal. Similar to the case of formula (2.39) in [33], formula (45) is simplified

$$\mu_l(\eta)_q = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} k_q^{-1/2} x_{l,q}^{1/2} \left[H_{l-\frac{1}{2}}^{(2)}(x_{l,q}) \right]. \quad (46)$$

Remark 3.1

It is important that solutions for $\mu_l(\eta)_q$ are different from the corresponding solutions of $\mu_l(\eta)$ in formula (2.35) [33] not only due to the multiplicative substitution $k \rightarrow k_q$, see (30), but also due to the multiplicative shift of the variable ($x_l = k\eta_l$) \rightarrow $x_{l,q} = k_q \eta_l = a_q \omega = \exp(\frac{1}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M})) x_l$. But, since $kx_l = k_q x_{l,q}$, in fact $\mu_l(\eta)_q = \mu_l(k_q, \eta)$ differs from $\mu_l(\eta) = \mu_l(k, \eta)$ in formulae (45) and (46) only by the M_q -shifted argument of the Hankel functions, i.e. $H_{l-\frac{1}{2}}^{(i)}(x_l) \mapsto H_{l-\frac{1}{2}}^{(i)}(x_{l,q}), i = 1, 2$.

So, in the natural pattern for the creation mechanism of **RGWs** [35],[32],[33] the M_q -deformation may shift significantly some important parameters with retention of the

principal results. According to formula (42) the M_q -**deformation** maintains the principal assumptions [32],[33], specifically concerning the fact that the right side of Einstein equations is the stress-energy tensor of a perfect fluid of the barotropic index γ_r , where r is indexing the constant γ in(39) for different stages which the Universe passes through during its expansion process. It is clear that an assumption of infinitesimal transition time periods between different stages, compared with time of each stage, is retained by the M_q -**deformation**. Then, as a

solution for the M_q -**deformation** of the Lifshitz equation (31), we have (46).

Within the scope of the M_q -**deformation**, from the above formulae it is inferred that the principal parameters associated with the process of **RGWs** formation are "enhanced" (i.e. multiplied by the value of > 1) compared to the canonical case.

3.1.1 The adiabatic bound for the frequencies at $\eta > \eta_i$, (formula (2.43) in [33])

$$\omega_i(\eta) = \frac{a_i}{a(\eta)} H_i \rightarrow \omega_i(\eta)_q = 2\pi \frac{a_{i,q}}{a(\eta)_q} H_{i,q} = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) \omega_i(\eta) > \omega_i(\eta). \quad (47)$$

3.1.2 In accordance, the energy of each created **RGW** $2\omega(\eta) \rightarrow 2\omega(\eta)_q$ is increased as well as the energy density of **RGWs** created at

the transition η_i , with frequencies in the range $[\omega(\eta)_q, \omega(\eta)_q + d\omega(\eta)_q]$, (formula (2.44) in [33])

$$\begin{aligned} d\rho_g(\eta) &= 2\omega(\eta) \left[\frac{\omega^2(\eta)}{2\pi^2} d\omega(\eta) \right] |\beta_i|^2 \\ \rightarrow d\rho_g(\eta)_q &= 2\omega(\eta)_q \left[\frac{\omega^2(\eta)_q}{2\pi^2} d\omega(\eta)_q \right] |\beta_i|^2 = P(\omega(\eta)_q) d\omega(\eta)_q = \exp\left(-2W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) P(\omega(\eta)) d\omega(\eta), \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

where $P(\omega(\eta)_q) = (\omega_q^3(\eta)/\pi^2) |\beta_i|^2 = \exp(-\frac{3}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M})) P(\omega(\eta))$ is the power spectrum in the M_q -**deformed** consideration and $P(\omega(\eta))$ – the same spectrum in the canonical pattern.

allowance is made for the fact that $d\omega(\eta)_q = \exp(-\frac{1}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M})) d\omega(\eta)$.

At the same time, the M_q -**deformed** total energy density passes to the domain of higher energies as compared with the canonical pattern

As follows from the last formula, $P(\omega(\eta)_q) > P(\omega(\eta))$. In the last term of the formula (48) an

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_g(\eta)_q &= \int_{2\pi H(\eta)_q}^{\omega_i(\eta)_q} P(\omega(\eta)_q) d\omega(\eta)_q = \exp\left(-2W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) \int_{2\pi H(\eta)_q}^{\omega_i(\eta)_q} P(\omega(\eta)) d\omega(\eta) \\ &= \exp\left(-2W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) \int_{2\pi H(\eta) \exp(-\frac{1}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}))}^{\exp(-\frac{1}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}))\omega_i(\eta)} P(\omega(\eta)) d\omega(\eta). \end{aligned} \tag{49}$$

Remark 3.2

Note that Bogoliubov transformation

$$\mu_{l_{r-1}}(\eta_i) = \alpha_i \mu_{l_r}(\eta_i) + \beta_i \mu_{l_r}^*(\eta_i). \tag{50}$$

relating the modes of the two above-mentioned consecutive stages ($r - 1$ and r -stages) remains

correct in M_q -**deformation**) in its initial form with the corresponding substitution in the last formula for

$$k \rightarrow k_q, \mu_{l_{r-1}}(\eta_i) \rightarrow \mu_{l_{r-1}}(\eta_i)_q, \mu_{l_r}(\eta_i) \rightarrow \mu_{l_r}(\eta_i)_q, \mu_{l_r}^*(\eta_i) \rightarrow \mu_{l_r}^*(\eta_i)_q \tag{51}$$

in virtue of (45),(46).

3.2. Power spectra of relic GWs within the scope of M_q -deformation

The results obtained in [32],[33] and [36] during studies of the power spectrum of relic GWs in the pattern of M_q -**deformation** are completely correct with due regard for the shifts M_q -**shifts** of the principal parameters derived in [13] (main formulae (18)-(21) in Section 2) and formulae involving k_q in subsection 3.1.

Indeed, for the Universe passing through three stages in the case of the spatially flat FRW

scenario (De Sitter stage followed by a radiation dominated era and a dust era that includes the present time) the scale factor in the canonical consideration is of the form (formulae (4) in [32] and (3.1) in [33]):

$$a(\eta) = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{H_1 \eta} & (-\infty < \eta < \eta_1 < 0), \\ \frac{1}{H_1 \eta_1^2} (\eta - 2\eta_1) & (\eta_1 < \eta < \eta_2), \\ \frac{1}{4H_1 \eta_1^2} \frac{(\eta + \eta_2 - 4\eta_1)^2}{\eta_2 - 2\eta_1} & (\eta_2 < \eta < \eta_0) \end{cases}, \tag{52}$$

which in the M_q -**deformed** pattern acquires the damping factor $\exp(\frac{1}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}))$:

$$a(\eta)_q = a(\eta) \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{H_{1,q} \eta} & (-\infty < \eta < \eta_1 < 0), \\ \frac{1}{H_{1,q} \eta_1^2} (\eta - 2\eta_1) & (\eta_1 < \eta < \eta_2), \\ \frac{1}{4H_{1,q} \eta_1^2} \frac{(\eta + \eta_2 - 4\eta_1)^2}{\eta_2 - 2\eta_1} & (\eta_2 < \eta < \eta_0) \end{cases}. \tag{53}$$

With the use of notation from [32],[33] H_1 , there is correspondence to H_0 from formulae (18),(19).

Returning to formulae (43)–(46), we can conclude

that in the present pattern the initial state is the M_q -**deformed** vacuum characterized by the modes of the inflationary stage $\mu_I(\eta)_q = \mu_I(k_q, \eta)$, which are a solution to the Lifshitz equation (31) compatible with the condition (38).

For the De Sitter stage, when $l = -1$, M_q -**shift**, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \{ \mu_I = (\sqrt{\pi}/2) e^{i\psi_I} k^{-1/2} x^{1/2} H_{-3/2}^{(2)}(x) \} \mapsto \\ \mapsto & \{ \mu_{I,q} = (\sqrt{\pi}/2) e^{i\psi_I} k_q^{-1/2} x_q^{1/2} H_{-3/2}^{(2)}(x_q) \}, \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

where $x = k\eta, x_q = k_q\eta, \psi_I$ is an arbitrary constant phase.

For the radiation era ($l = 1$), M_q -**shift** of the proper modes has form

$$\begin{aligned} & \{ \mu_R = (\sqrt{\pi}/2) e^{i\psi_R} k^{-1/2} x_R^{1/2} H_{1/2}^{(2)}(x_R) \} \mapsto \\ \mapsto & \{ \mu_{R,q} = (\sqrt{\pi}/2) e^{i\psi_R} k_q^{-1/2} x_{R,q}^{1/2} H_{1/2}^{(2)}(x_{R,q}) \} \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

where $x_R = k(\eta - 2\eta_1), x_{R,q} = k_q(\eta - 2\eta_1)$, and ψ_R is a constant phase again.

3.2.3 for a solution for the modes in the dust era ($\eta > \eta_2$ and $l = 2$, constant phase ψ_D), M_q -**shift**

$$\begin{aligned} & \{ \mu_D = (\sqrt{\pi}/2) e^{i\psi_D} k^{-1/2} x_D^{1/2} H_{3/2}^{(2)}(x_D) \} \mapsto \\ & \{ \mu_{D,q} = (\sqrt{\pi}/2) e^{i\psi_D} k_q^{-1/2} x_{D,q}^{1/2} H_{3/2}^{(2)}(x_{D,q}) \}, \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

where $x_D = k(\eta + \eta_2 - 4\eta_1), x_{D,q} = k_q(\eta + \eta_2 - 4\eta_1)$.

It should be noted that for all Hankel functions in formulae (54)–(56) the M_q -**deformed** Hankel functions are differing from the initial one only by substitution in the argument $k \rightarrow k_q$ in formula (30).

Remark 3.2 is true for (54)–(55) as the difference of the (canonical modes μ_I, μ_R, μ_D) considered in [32],[33] from the M_q -**shifted** modes $\mu_{I,q}, \mu_{R,q}, \mu_{D,q}$ consists *only* in substitution of the argument for the corresponding Hankel functions.

Substituting $k \rightarrow k_q$ in formulae ((3.4)–(3.9) in [33] or in the corresponding formulae of [32]), we can obtain the following M_q -**shift** of the present power spectrum $P(\omega)$ of GWs (formulae (18) in [32] and (3.10) in [33]) :

$$P(\omega)_q \sim \begin{cases} 0 & (\omega(\eta_0)_q > 2\pi(a_1/a_0)H_{1,q}), \\ \omega^{-1}(\eta_0)_q & (2\pi(a_2/a_0)H_{2,q} < \omega(\eta_0)_q < 2\pi(a_1/a_0)H_{1,q}), \\ \omega^{-3}(\eta_0)_q & (2\pi H_{pres,q} < \omega(\eta_0)_q < 2\pi(a_2/a_0)H_{2,q}). \end{cases} \quad (57)$$

In (57), similar to the subscript q , denotes the M_q -**shift** of the corresponding quantity; H_2 and H_{pres} is the Hubble parameter evaluated at the radiation-matter transition η_2 and at the present time, respectively, and $\omega(\eta_0)_q$ is the M_q -**shift** of the present value of the frequency:

$\omega(\eta_0)_q = k_q/a_{0,k} = \omega(\eta_0) = k/a_0$. In the relations $a_1/a_0, a_2/a_0$ of the last formula the index q was not used because, as stated in Section 2, these relations are retained with M_q -**shift**.

Based on the foregoing formulae, we can state that the M_q -**shift** $P(\omega)_q$ (formula (57)) retains the initial power spectrum $P(\omega)$ in all the domains of definition (57)) as $\omega(\eta_0)_q = \omega(\eta_0)$, but the M_q -**shift** increases boundaries of these domains.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, based on the results from [12]-[14] it has been demonstrated that the M_q -**deformation** created by **qgcs** for **qpbh** with the mass M in the early Universe during the pre-inflation period can shift the principal parameters of Relic Gravitational Waves. As this takes place, some parameters obtain higher values (for example, the adiabatic bound for the frequencies at the same time and energy of each generated **RGW**). Other parameters retain the values but their domains of definition are shifted (present power spectrum of **RGWs**)).

The author is planning further studies of **RGWs** within the scope of different scenarios:

(a) emissions of **qpbh**;

(b) generation of several **qpbh**;

(c)merging of them and subsequent emission.

As inflation cosmology and gravitational-wave astronomy are the fields attracting more and more attention of the researchers, the formulated problem may be of interest for future precise experiments related to this sphere. Besides, it is interesting to consider the inverse problem, namely to determine **qpbhs**, which give these parameters with due regard for **qgcs**, *using the parameters of RGWs*.

Conflict of Interests

The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this work.

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